
The Implementation of Language Rules Learning in the Framework of Students' Indonesian Language Text Production at SMPN, West Lombok District

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Abstract

This study aims to describe the application of linguistic rules learning within the framework of Indonesian language text production and the results of the application of linguistic rules learning within the framework of Indonesian language text production for junior high school students in West Lombok District. This research is a development research, that is the application of linguistic rules learning in Indonesian language subjects in junior high schools. In collecting data, observation, interviews, documentation, and triangulation methods were used. The method used to analyze the data was a qualitative descriptive method, using content analysis techniques or content studies. Based on the results of the data analysis, it was found that the types of linguistic rules learning taught in Indonesian language subjects depend on the type of text presented. The implementation of linguistic rules learning is carried out specifically and applicatively. The implementation of the development of linguistic rules teaching materials is largely determined by the characteristics of students and the creativity of teachers in each respective school. In general, students' abilities in constructing text ideas can be said to be good. However, there is still a need for a comprehensive deepening of mastery of linguistic rules concepts that form the basic foundation in producing texts.

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1. Introduction

Learning aims to optimally improve a student's abilities, which must be implemented through a variety of structured and measurable steps. A good learning structure is one that is implemented in stages, from simple to complex steps. A learning system is essentially a means to achieve learning objectives, that is, students achieving maximum learning outcomes in learning activities.

Classroom learning is a diverse event. Among them are a planned and sequential curriculum unit, or an example of the application of teaching methods, patterns of social activity that occur in the classroom, and the meeting of various human personalities, many things happen in a particular class that describe routine activities that do not change and can unite various different demands from various different dimensions for certain teachers and language learners under our direction (Prabhu, in Ghzali, 2010: 1).

The learning objectives serve as a gauge for the effectiveness of the teaching and learning process. Essentially, the curriculum is a tool for achieving learning objectives. The curriculum is a set of guidelines used by teachers in the learning process. Therefore, the curriculum is essential for teachers at all times in determining the direction of learning activities in the classroom, from preparation, implementation, and evaluation.

In line with the development of science and technology, changes in the curriculum will be followed. These changes also impact changes in Indonesian language learning, particularly in the implementation of learning approaches. For example, the 2006 Curriculum and the 2008 Curriculum (KTSP) continues to use a communicative approach, similar to the 1994 curriculum. This communicative approach places greater emphasis on how language is used to communicate. Language rules are learned through communication according to the context in which the language is used. Therefore, because every use of language always involves many rules, Indonesian language learning always selects which linguistic rules need to be emphasized in the material being studied. In other words, learning linguistic aspects is always inductive (Pranowo, 2015:54).

Pranowo further cited traditional linguistic assumptions, one of which states that language must be correct based on rules. Language is fundamentally about expressing thoughts and feelings. Therefore, if the rules are used incorrectly, the thoughts and feelings expressed will be incorrect and unclear. This demonstrates that the use of language rules is a crucial component in language use.

Developing comprehension and reasoning skills is fundamental to students' general learning activities. The way students use language will influence their social, emotional, physical, and cognitive development. Students' success in various fields such as science, social science, and mathematics depends on their ability to understand and construct language based on their level of reasoning ability. To achieve a high level of proficiency, they need to be given opportunities to practice, express their own meaning, interact, use language creatively, and carry out a wide range of functions related to a number of topics (Ghazali, 2010:43). Students' expression of meaning can be realized in written form, in this case in the form of text. The term "text" is often used interchangeably with the term "discourse." Discourse is an abstract theoretical construct, while text is the concrete manifestation of language use. Therefore, discourse is not seen as a physical manifestation of language. The manifestation of language is text.

Based on the results of research conducted by Sudika et al. (2023), the material on language rules is taught depending on the type of text being taught at that time. Learning language rules shows that the allocation of learning time is still minimal because the learning is emphasized on the demands of students to maximize their understanding of the content of the reading or text they read. Whereas in other aspects of language skills such as skills also really need attention and are an obligation for students to master them. Therefore, mastery of language rules is very necessary for students as a basic foundation in the framework of composing ideas expressed in

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written or text form. The text that is constructed should follow a structured, systematic arrangement and in accordance with language rules in written language. Thus, this study is considered important to conduct further research to obtain an overview of the results of the application of language rules learning in the framework of developing Indonesian language text production for junior high school (SMP) students. This study aims to describe the application of language rules learning in the framework of Indonesian language text production and to determine the results of the application of language rules learning in the framework of Indonesian language text production for junior high school students in West Lombok Regency. The results of this study are expected to be particularly useful as a result of the application of linguistic rules learning within the framework of improving students' ability to compose or produce Indonesian language texts and can help teachers in the process of text-based Indonesian language learning at the Junior High School (SMP) level, especially in West Lombok.

2. Method

This type of research is included in the type of development research (Sugiono, 2009:5), that is applying linguistic rules learning to Indonesian language subjects in junior high school. This research provides a basic foundation to help Indonesian language teachers improve the quality of their teaching and develop students' abilities in writing or constructing Indonesian language texts.

This research is qualitative research, because the data collected in this study is qualitative descriptive data, data in the form of documents, field notes, statements and actions of respondents (Sugiono, 2009:23). This is in line with what was stated by Subroto (2007:5) that the data collected in qualitative research is soft data. The data collected in this study are document data and learning activities for Indonesian language teachers at SMPN in West Lombok Regency. The data source for this study is the results of activities carried out by Indonesian language teachers in a language rules learning activity. The results of these learning activities will be used to formulate patterns for developing language rules learning. Several methods will be used in data collection, that is: observation, interviews, documentation, and triangulation. These four methods can be explained as follows.

Observation Method

The observation method that will be used in this research is the participant observation method. This method used because the researcher is involved with the activities of the teachers being observed or used as a source of research data (Sugiono, 2009:310). The data to be obtained through the participatory observation method is in the form of the results of the teacher's activities in implementing the learning of linguistic rules in the Indonesian language subject within the framework of producing texts for students.

Triangulation Method

The triangulation method was also used in data collection. This method relies on the same data source using several different techniques, that is the results of teachers' activities in implementing linguistic rules in Indonesian language learning. Furthermore, this method can be used to collect data from multiple sources using a single data collection technique.

The method used to analyze the data in this study is a qualitative descriptive method, using content analysis techniques or content studies (Moleong, 2014:220). In this data analysis activity, a domain analysis will be conducted to obtain a general overview of the application of language rules learning in Indonesian language learning. Next, a taxonomic analysis will be conducted to obtain a more specific picture of the research data sources obtained (Sugiyono, 2009:348). The steps to be taken in the data analysis process are as follows.

In the first stage, researchers examine all data obtained through observations with the aim of identifying information that is relevant to the research problem. Once the data has been identified, it is then analyzed using methods and techniques appropriate to its nature. If the data aligns with the research objective domain, a qualitative descriptive method can be employed to describe the implementation of the learning pattern model.

The following step involves classifying the data according to its function, where the information is grouped into specific categories. Finally, conclusions are drawn based on the results of the data analysis, providing answers to the research questions and insights into the studied phenomenon.

3. Results and Discussion

Based on data collected through observation and interview methods on the Indonesian language learning process in junior high schools, especially related to text-based language rules learning. In this study, two schools were used as research samples, that is SMPN 1 Kuripan and SMPN 2 Batu Layar Lombok which were targeted at Indonesian language learning in class VIII, with the consideration that in class VIII, language rules learning is taught as a development of learning in class VII. The results of this study can be described regarding: (1) types of language rules learning in Indonesian language texts taught in junior high school classes, (2) the application of language rules learning, and (3) the results of the application of language rules learning. These three things are successively described below.

Types of Learning Language Rules in Texts

The types of linguistic rules taught in Indonesian depend on the type of text presented. The types of linguistic rules in texts discussed specifically in grade VIII can be seen in the following table.

Table 1
Learning Language Rules in Texts

No.	Text Type Name	Linguistic Rules
1.	Learning Observation Report (LHO) text	(1) use of a noun as the main object, (2) use of certain terms, (3) use of descriptive sentences, (4) use of definition sentences, (5) use of conjunctions, use of adjectives. (6) Identifying Descriptive and Expository Paragraphs (7) Use of punctuation, and (8) Writing foreign and regional language words.
2.	Learning advertising texts, slogans and posters	(1) persuasive sentences or invitations, (2) imperative sentences or commands, and

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		(3) interrogative or question sentences.
3.	Learning to Write Popular Scientific Articles	Comparative Sentences, Analogy Sentences, Synonyms and Antonyms
4.	Learning to Review Fictional Texts	Denotative words and Connotation words
5.	Learning to create poetry	Comparing metaphors Simile and repetition
6.	Learning to write speech texts	Persuasive Sentences Expression of Concern or Sympathy

The table above shows that learning linguistic rules is more specific and applicable. Specific learning is defined as limited to the needs of the text being taught, while applicative learning involves the direct use of linguistic rules in the learning of specific texts that serve as reference points for the main learning material. In this context, students are assumed to understand all linguistic rules concepts and be able to use them in the required discourse context.

The linguistic rules detailed in the table above cannot all be taught in a single session, as each session requires completing several learning objectives. Meanwhile, in subsequent sessions, new material will be introduced using different text types. Consequently, students' mastery of all aspects of linguistic rules will be less than optimal.

Application of Language Rules in Learning

Currently, almost all junior high schools have implemented the Independent Curriculum. By implementing this curriculum, particularly in Indonesian language learning, each teacher delivers Indonesian language learning materials, whether related to strategies, methods, media selection, or material development. Furthermore, the implementation of teaching material development is also highly determined by the characteristics of each school and is largely determined by the teacher's ability and taste in developing the material. Likewise, student learning motivation varies across classes; there are often high, medium, and low motivations. All of these factors can contribute to variations in the learning process, particularly in the learning of linguistic rules in Indonesian language lessons.

At SMPN 1 Kuripan, teachers begin teaching language rules by explaining the text structure and language rules. After students are deemed to have understood the explanation, the teacher provides a worksheet (LKPD) on the language rules of observation report texts (LHO) to be worked on in groups.

The LKPD describes the following matters.

- (1) Learning objectives, that is students can identify linguistic rules in LHO texts and can use appropriate linguistic rules in composing LHO texts.
- (2) Learning steps
 - a. Introduction:
 - The teacher explains the learning objectives
 - The teacher gives an example of a LHO text and explains the structure of the text and its linguistic rules.
 - b. Core Activities:
 - Students read the LHO text given.
 - Student identify the linguistic rules contained in the text.
 - Students discuss in groups to discuss the results of identifying linguistic rules.

- Students compose LHO texts using correct linguistic rules.

c. Closing Activities

- Teachers and student sreflect on the learning that has been carried out
- Teacher provide feedback on student work results.

(3) Linguistic rules that must be identified

- Use of definition and description sentences
- Use of common nouns (Nominal) and material verbs
- Use of adjectives to provide a more detailed description
- Use of conjunctions to connect sentences.

On the description above, students learn linguistic rules by identifying the elements contained in the text. This identification ability is expected to enable students to use all types of linguistic rules to construct a complete text.

The learning model applied at SMPN 2 Batu Layar is different from the learning model used by Indonesian Language teachers at SMPN 1 Kuripan. In the learning activities with the material of linguistic rules in advertising texts, slogans and posters. The first thing the teacher does is each student is asked to find examples of forms of advertising that are directly encountered in everyday life by observing and recording the words or sentences contained in the advertisement. The results of student notes through these observations, that is regarding sentences in the advertising text, are then discussed together as learning material carried out in the classroom.

In class discussion learning, the teacher classifies each word or sentence found by students and writes it on the board. Next, the teacher explains which words or sentences are classified as imperative sentences (*commands*), persuasive sentences (*invitations*), and interrogative sentences (*questions*). The types of sentences that have been found and mentioned by students are assisted by the teacher to write on the board by classifying whether the sentence is included as an advertisement sentence, slogan, or poster. The classification of these sentences is the sentence rules that are often used and found in an advertisement text, slogan, and poster. In this learning meeting, the focus is on the material of advertising texts with the characteristics of their linguistic rules. The next step, the teacher gives students the task of composing an advertising text using sentence rules as characteristics of advertising, that is persuasive sentences, imperative sentences, and interrogative sentences.

From observing the application of learning linguistic rules in texts show that the instilling of basic concepts about linguistic rules to students needs to be developed further. By mastering linguistic rules, students can develop them and use them appropriately in composing various types of texts they want. In this regard, the development of linguistic rules can be carried out by teachers to enrich the vocabulary of learning linguistic rules in composing texts. The concept that can be used is the concept developed by Ferdinand de Saussure, a Structural Linguistics expert, in one of his relevant dichotomies, that is syntagmatic and paradigmatic relationships. Syntagmatic relationships are horizontal developments, the arrangement of words with other words that form a sentence structure and have a meaningful relationship (Pranowo. 2015:61, and Saussure, 1993:221). Paradigmatic relationships or associative relationships are the arrangement of one sound with another sound that forms a word and has different meanings and sound elements used. In fact, this paradigmatic relationship does not only apply to sound sequences but can be applied in vertical relationships in terms of the relationship of one word to another in a sentence which shows an association relationship.

Example:

(1) *Kucing memiliki mata yang unik.*

Sentence (1) above can be developed syntax matically into the following sentence (1a).

(1a) *Kucing memiliki mata yang unik dan berfungsi mencari mangsa.*

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The unique lingual unit relationship of the *mata yang unik* in sentence (1a) as a syntagmatic relationship with the group functions to *berfungsi mencari mangsa*.

(2) *Kucing memiliki kumis.*

(3) *Gajah memiliki belalai.*

The word *kucing* in sentence (2) and *gajah* in sentence (3) above are paradigmatic relationships or associative relationships, likewise the word *kumis* in sentence (2) and the word *belalai* in sentence (3) are paradigmatic relationships. Thus, these two concepts can be applied in the development of language rule learning to help improve students' abilities in composing and developing vocabulary in building the structure of an Indonesian language text.

Results of the application of linguistic rules learning

The results of the application of linguistic rules learning in text composition learning can be seen in several examples of text excerpts written by students themselves. The results of this text writing are a continuation of the previous learning process by carrying out learning steps to identify linguistic rules contained in the text, then continued by applying them in composing texts using definition sentences and descriptive sentences in the text as in the following examples.

Definition sentences in text

(4) *Sekolah SDN 3 Kuripan adalah sekolah yang sangat ramah dan baik, sekolah SDN3 kuripan berada di pinggir SMPN 1 Kuripan Dusun Sedayu, kecamatan kuripan, Jalan Tgh. Abdul Hafiz melewati bai pas.*

(5) *Pantai Kuta adalah salah satu wisata di Lombok Tengah. Pantai kuta memiliki parkir yang cukup luas dan memiliki taman bermain. Pantai Kuta sangat banyak dikunjungi oleh orang-orang karena pantai kuta sangat indah.*

(6) *SMP Negeri 1 Kuripan adalah salah satu sekolah yang terletak di kabupaten Lombok barat SMP ini terletak di desa kuripan dusun sedayu.*

(7) *Pasar kuripan terletak di samping kantor desa kuripan. pasar ini merupakan pasar yang sangat luas dan banyak dagang yang sangat murah hati pasar kuripan memiliki pedagang mas yang sangat banyak.*

Sentences (4) to (7) above are excerpts from the text written by students. The text is a definition sentence from the beginning of the student's observation report text. The sentences that are composed already show the right idea as a definition sentence. However, students are not yet able to distinguish between topic sentences and explanatory sentences which can actually be composed of one paragraph text. Meanwhile, the ideas in the text should be arranged into several sentences. Each sentence should start with a capital letter and end the sentence using final intonation. Likewise, the use of capital letters at the beginning of words that indicate place names (village names, sub-districts, and regencies) should use capital letters, such as the words Kuta, Sedayu, , Kuripan, and West Lombok which are found in sentences (5), (6), and (7). This kind of concept of linguistic rules needs to be instilled in students as a basic foundation for building broader language units, so that students are able to compose good texts using correct linguistic rules.

If sentence (4) above is corrected, it will become the following paragraph (4a). (4a) *Sekolah SDN 3 Kuripan adalah sekolah yang sangat ramah dan baik. Sekolah ini berada di samping kiri SMPN 1 Kuripan yang juga berlokasi di Jalan Tgh. Abdul Hafiz. Dusun Sedayu, Kecamatan Kuripan.*

Descriptive sentences in text

- (8) Sekolah ini juga cukup luas dan memiliki lumayan banyak siswa yang bersekolah di sana dan memiliki banyak ruang kelas untuk siswa-siswa SDN 3 Kuripan belajar.
- (9) SMPN 1 Kuripan ini anak muridnya banyak sekali dan siswa-siswi ramai dan banyak siswa-siswi di sini ajari sopan santun terhadap orang tua dan guru, siswa-siswi di sini tidak pernah membantah sebaiknya siswa-siswi di sini sangat patuh apa yang disuruh sama bapak guru dan ibu guru. Siswa-siswi di sini sangat senang karena SMPN 1 Kuripan banyak teman2 yang sangat baik dan ramah di sini.
- (10) Sekolah tersebut memiliki 1 kantor (ruang guru) dan ada ruangan yang khusus untuk rapat dan memperhatikan siswa dan ketertiban seluruh siswa dan mempunyai fasilitas yang cukup untuk siswa.
- (11) Sekolah ini sangatlah ramai dan juga muridnya sangatlah banyak sampai2 gak ada kelas kosong, makanya kelas 1 dan 2 itu giliran masuknya ada yang jam 07.00 ada juga jam 09.00

In general, students have demonstrated the ability to construct ideas in the form of descriptive sentence texts. This indicates that they already possess the basic competence required to organize thoughts and express them in written form. However, several weaknesses were identified that need further attention and improvement. One recurring issue lies in the use of spelling. For example, some students began their sentences with lowercase letters, as seen in sentence (8). Such errors suggest a lack of consistency in applying standard writing conventions, which is a crucial aspect of academic writing.

Another notable weakness concerns the cohesion of ideas within a text. Some students still struggle to connect sentences within a single idea, resulting in fragmented expressions that reduce the overall clarity of the text. This reflects the need for students to strengthen their understanding of how to use conjunctions and cohesive devices effectively. Without these skills, their writing tends to appear disjointed and less communicative.

The analysis also revealed the influence of spoken language on students' writing. Words that are commonly used in daily conversation, such as *cukup* in sentence (8), *sekolahan* in sentence (11), and *gak* in sentence (11), were inappropriately transferred into written texts. This demonstrates that students have not yet fully distinguished between spoken and written registers of language, a distinction that is essential for producing formal written texts.

In addition, errors were found in the writing of repeated words. Several students used numerical symbols, such as "2," to represent reduplication, producing forms like *teman2* and *sampai2* in sentences (9) and (11). According to standard writing rules, these should be written in full as *teman-teman* and *sampai-sampai*. Such practices reflect the informal habits often seen in digital communication, such as texting or social media, which then carry over into academic writing.

Overall, while students show promising ability in generating descriptive ideas, the presence of these errors highlights the importance of reinforcing the mastery of spelling, cohesion, register, and formal conventions of written Indonesian. Addressing these weaknesses through targeted instruction and practice will not only improve the accuracy of their writing but also enhance their ability to produce texts that meet academic and professional standards.

4. Conclusion

Based on the discussion above, this section concludes that the types of language rules taught in Indonesian language subjects depend on the type of text presented. Language rules learning is more specific and applicable. Specific learning is defined as the scope of language material learning limited to the suitability of the text being presented, while applicative learning is defined

as the direct use of language rules in learning specific texts that serve as a reference for the main learning material.

By implementing the Independent Curriculum, particularly in Indonesian language learning, each teacher delivers Indonesian language learning materials, whether related to strategies, methods, media selection, or material development. The implementation of teaching materials is also highly determined by the characteristics of each school and is highly determined by the teacher's abilities and preferences in developing their teaching materials. In general, students' ability to construct ideas in text form can be said to be good. However, there is still a need for students to deepen their mastery of comprehensive linguistic concepts. Through mastery of these linguistic concepts, it is hoped that students will be able to construct linguistic units in the form of cohesive and coherent texts using correct linguistic rules.

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